

TRANSFORMATION OF REAL SECTOR GOVERNANCE ORIENTATION OF JOINT BUSINESS AND TRANSFER OF SOCIAL MEDIA TECHNOLOGY ON THE PERFORMANCE OF MICRO SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES CULINARY IMPACT OF THE COVID- 19 PANDEMIC IN SOUTH SULAWESI INDONESIA

HASANUDDIN REMMANG

Universitas Bosowa. Email: hasanuddin_remmang@yahoo.com, remmanghasan@gmail.com

MUKMIN MUHAMMAD

STIA Al Gazali Barru. Email: mukmintomy48048@gmail.com

ACHMAD ANZHARI

Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Manajemen Lasharan Jaya. Email: anzharihasnud@gmail.com

ARNAS HASANUDDIN

Universitas Wira Bhakti. Email: arnashasanuddin94@gmail.com

ASKARI HASANUDDIN

Universitas Cahaya Proima. Email: askarihasanuddin@yahoo.com

Abstract

The focus of this research aims to determine the transformation of governance in the real joint business sector and social media technology transfer on the performance of culinary businesses after the Covid-19 pandemic in South Sulawesi under the guidance of the South Sulawesi Cooperatives and Small Business Service and the influence of social media as a moderating variable in the relationship between joint business and technology transfer. Social information on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the real sector. Research data was obtained from 350 respondents who were Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises assisted by the South Sulawesi Cooperatives and Small Business Service in 2023. The research was carried out by distributing questionnaires via Google Forms and the data was processed using Partial Least Square (PLS). The research results show that the transformation of governance in the real (culinary) sector, orientation towards joint business and technology transfer on social media, has an influence on business performance in the culinary sector after the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. In this research, it was also found that technology transfer for digital marketing in the social media variable did not moderate the relationship between customer orientation and the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises during the post-Covid-19 pandemic period.

Keywords: Joint, Business, Technology Transfer, Business, Micro, Medium.

INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 pandemic that hit Indonesia has had a significant impact on all sectors of the economy. Various types of businesses have felt quite a strong impact, although there are still several business groups that can take advantage and benefit from this pandemic condition. One

of the business groups most affected by Covid-19 is Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises). This is a concern because Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises themselves are the largest contributor to GDP in Indonesia at 60.34% and absorb 96.9% of the total employment (Maulidah, 2021).

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises have responded in several ways so that they can survive in the post-Covid-19 pandemic. The method most often used by Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises from surveys conducted by previous researchers regarding the impact of Covid-19 is to carry out digitalization steps, namely carrying out marketing from offline to online, and followed by changing/creating new products/businesses, getting additional capital, HR efficiency, production cost efficiency and others (Pusparisa, 2020).

The transition of marketing from offline to online is one of the strategies to survive in the post-pandemic conditions, supported by the number of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises that are connected to digital platforms. According to data from the Ministry of Cooperatives and Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, there are 16.4 million Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises connected to digital platforms by 2023. This figure has increased 100% since the start of the pandemic in 2019, where the Minister of Cooperatives and Micro Enterprises Small and Medium Enterprises Teten Masduki said that in the midst of the uncertainty and critical situation during the pandemic which resulted in the economy weakening, business transformation to digital has become very important for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. This allows Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises to survive and continue to contribute and improve the country's economy (CNNI Indonesia, 2023).

South Sulawesi Province is one of the eastern provinces of Indonesia which plays an important role in the Indonesian economy. This is shown by the South Sulawesi region covering 20% of the total territory of Indonesia, and what is interesting is that 98.5% of the economic drivers in South Sulawesi are Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (Bella, 2018). According to the Head of the South Sulawesi Provincial Cooperatives and Small Business Service (KUK), Dr. Ashari Rajdamilo.MSi, the income of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in South Sulawesi decreased drastically by 80 percent after the Covid-19 pandemic. This has led Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises to digitalize with the aim of surviving amidst the uncertain conditions caused by the pandemic. It has been recorded that the growth of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises that digitalized was 40% during the post-Covid-19 pandemic. . This phenomenon is caused by people's shopping behavior in South Sulawesi shifting from offline to online which continues to increase in the post-pandemic period (Wijayanto, 2021).

Dekopin South Sulawesi has a superior program to develop Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in this area, namely the Champion Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises program. The benefits obtained by Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises that take part in this program are self-strengthening and business management for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises to be able to move up in class. Apart from that, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises will receive assistance to utilize technology in business to reach the market (Nurranirusmana, 2024). One of the sectors listed as being supported by DEKOPIN South Sulawesi is the culinary sector.

However, according to a statement from one of the staff who manages the Juara Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, the culinary sector was the sector worst affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. This is due to several regulations and restrictions for selling directly so that consumers cannot come directly to the location.

Dekopin as the Indonesian cooperative council for South Sulawesi which oversees Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises and provides several training and mentoring methods for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises to survive and develop in the post-Covid-19 pandemic period. One of the trainings is to carry out marketing training for the staff so they can continue to market their products well and maintain good relationships with their customers. Apart from that, training for the use of social media digital marketing systems is also carried out so that the coaches can better market their products by digitalizing them.

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises assisted by Dekopin South Sulawesi already have their own social media for business and have the basic skills to operate it, but their use is still felt to be insufficient and needs to be improved. Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises tend to only have social media for their business and upload a few photos of their products and provide less information about their business. This makes customers who view the social media of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises less interested so that the use of social media feels less effective.

Being customer oriented is important for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises to be able to understand what customers want. This is the basis for increasing sales and profits so that Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises that have knowledge about what customers want, will be better able to compete and improve their performance compared to competitors (Nurfarida et. al., 2021).

The use of social media by Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises is one option that can be used to find out what customers want. Customer orientation or joint business which involves internal factors or factors from outside the company such as technology development, one of which is social media, is important to do (Nurfarida et al., 2021).

Based on the explanation of the phenomenon and background above, in this research the researcher raised the title "Transformation of real sector governance with an orientation towards joint business and social media technology transfer after the Covid-19 Pandemic (Study of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Assisted by the Cooperative Service and South Sulawesi Small Businesses in 2023 Culinary Sector)".

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

The following is an explanation of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises based on Law Number 20 of 2008 concerning Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises:

- a) Micro Business is a productive business owned by an individual and/or individual business entity that meets the criteria for Micro Business. The criteria for being considered a micro business are having net assets of a maximum of IDR 50,000,000 excluding land and buildings where the business is located and having an annual turnover of a maximum of IDR 300,000,000.

- b) Small business is a stand-alone productive economic business carried out by an individual or business entity that is not a subsidiary or branch of a company that is owned, controlled, or is part, either directly or indirectly, of a medium or large business, with The criteria are having a net worth of a maximum of IDR 50,000,000 to a maximum of IDR 500,000,000 excluding land and buildings for business premises and also having an annual turnover of more than IDR 300,000,000 to IDR 2,500,000,000.
- c) Medium Business is a productive economic business that stands alone and is carried out by an individual or business entity that is not a subsidiary or branch of a company that is owned, controlled, or part of, either directly or indirectly, a Small Business or Enterprise. Big with the amount of net assets or annual sales proceeds as regulated in this law. The criteria for a medium-sized business is to have a net worth of more than IDR 500,000,000 to a maximum of IDR 10,000,000,000 excluding land and business premises and also to have an annual turnover of more than IDR 2,500,000,000 to a maximum of IDR 50,000,000. 000.

Dynamic Capabilities

According to Situmorang (2018), dynamic capability or sweet capability is the ability of a company to integrate, build and reconfigure competencies internally and externally in facing dynamic and rapid environmental changes. Dynamic capabilities are reflected as strategies that release old resources and integrate them to produce new resources (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000).

According to Teece in Nurfarida et al. (2021) the concept of dynamic capability is an expanded concept to understand how a company can achieve competitive advantage due to technological developments and also facing an uncertain environment. These erratic and rapid environmental changes are a result of advances in information technology, which can be explained by the concept of dynamic capabilities (Lin & Wu, 2014).

Joint Business/Customer Orientation

According to Nurfarida et al. (2021) explain that customer orientation is a company's ability to identify, understand and respond to what the market wants with the aim of achieving competitive advantage. Companies that have a strong customer orientation tend to prioritize the needs of their customers for the current and future (Ziggers & Henseler, 2016). Being customer-oriented will attract customers to buy products and services which will increase the company's opportunity to grow (Neneh, 2018).

Meanwhile Lubis et al. (2020) explain that customer orientation is a type of organizational orientation where the needs of consumers are the basis for an organization to be able to plan or design its business strategy. Customer orientation can be used more successfully in small companies because of the more natural interaction between business owners and consumers than that experienced by large companies (Brockman et al., 2012). Meanwhile, according to Islam & Zhe (2022), customer-oriented organizations will lead to new services or product development, where these activities will have an impact on organizational performance.

Transfer Technology

Technology transfer is defined as a marketing transfer system that is oriented towards customers and potential consumers and business digital internet-based capability resources that enable their use to strengthen the synergy of an organization (Nasrullah, 2015). The importance of using social media in an organization in various fields, namely research and development, sales, customer support, operations, and also marketing (Fan et al., 2021).

The impact of using social media with technology transfer with digital marketing tools is in terms of purchasing decisions by consumers, where the use of social media can increase brand recognition and get feedback from consumers, which provides benefits for business actors for market research data. (Ahmad et al., 2019). Social media itself has special characteristics that other media do not have, where according to Nasrullah (2015) the characteristics of social media are network, information, archive, interaction, social simulation. of society), and user-generated content. The following is an explanation of each of these characteristics.

a. Network

Social media has the characteristics of a social network. The word network can be understood in technological terminology such as computer science, which means infrastructure that connects computers and hardware with other computers. The network that is formed ultimately forms a community, for example Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, etc. (Nasrullah, 2015).

b. Information

Information is a very important entity in social media. Different from other media on the internet, social media users present their identities, produce content, and also interact based on information. Information has also become a commodity in the information society. Information on social media is produced, exchanged and consumed by every individual on social media (Nasrullah, 2015)

c. Archives

Archives are a characteristic that explains that information that has been stored by social media users can be accessed at any time and via any device. Any information uploaded and shared by social media users does not just disappear, whether in days, months or years (Nasrullah, 2015).

d. Interaction

The basic characteristic of social media is the formation of a network between users. This network was built because of interactions between users on social media. Interaction is a process that occurs between users and technological devices. In this way, the presence of technology, in this case social media, becomes something that cannot be separated from everyday life (Nasrullah, 2015).

e. Social Simulation (Simulation of Society)

In the process of interaction between users that occurs on social media through an interface, users must go through two conditions. First, social media users must connect to be in cyber space, namely by logging in or entering the social media they use by writing down their

username and password. Second, when users are on social media, users sometimes involve openness in their self-identity as well as directing how the individual can identify or describe themselves virtually on social media (Nasrullah, 2015). Social media has become a medium or means for people to exchange information and interact, both as a tool for communication and as a promotional medium in business. There are several types of social media that are widely used by people. The types of social media are as follows:

a. YouTube

Basically, YouTube is a digital platform in the form of a website and application where the main feature is to facilitate users to share the videos they own or simply enjoy various video clips uploaded by other parties (Abdullah et al., 2023).

b. Facebook

Facebook is a social networking site that allows its users to interact with each other throughout the world. Facebook offers several advanced features that have never been available on social media before. Apart from the message exchange feature, other features are that users can create personal pages, add friends, share various types of content, selling, and so on (Shakir et al., 2023).

c. Instagram

Instagram is a photo sharing service application that allows its users to take photos and provide filters, then distribute them on the Instagram social network and can be seen by other Instagram users (Atmoko, 2012).

d. TikTok

TikTok is a social networking application and music video platform where users can create, edit and also share short video clips complete with several filter features and accompanied by music as support. With this application, users can create unique short videos quickly and easily (Choudhary et al., 2020).

e. Twitter

Twitter is a social networking service or can also be called an online microblog that allows its users to send, read and reply to texts of up to 280 characters. The texts written by users are usually referred to as tweets (Anber et al., 2016).

Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

According to Neneh (2018) the performance of a company is a very multidimensional thing where the measurement of a company's performance is usually measured from financial and non-financial based indicators. Zhu & Nakata (2007) stated that company performance which is influenced by customer orientation can be strengthened by the ability to use IT. A company's performance can be measured from several indicators, namely increasing market share in a certain period, increasing sales in a certain period, and achieving profits from a certain period (Nurfarida et al., 2021).

Company performance is a very important criterion in evaluating companies which is measured by comparing company performance from the previous year (Dharmawati, 2016). Financial factors are something that is very important to pay attention to when discussing the performance of a company (Lubis et al., 2020). A similar thing was also stated by Akmese et al., (2016) where the performance of a company can be measured through financial performance with the use of social media being a factor in improving its performance.

Research Model

- H1: Customer orientation with joint business agreements has a significant effect on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the culinary sector of South Sulawesi during the post-Covid-19 pandemic period.
- H2: Social media has a significant influence on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the culinary sector in Salatan Sulawesi during the post-Covid-19 pandemic period.
- H3: Social media has a significant influence in strengthening the relationship between customer orientation and the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the culinary sector in South Sulawesi during the post-Covid-19 pandemic period.

Research Population and Sample

The population in this research is all Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises assisted by Dekopin South Sulawesi in the culinary sector in 2023, totaling 2,168 units. Sampling was carried out using the Slovin formula where the calculation results were as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Gambar 1: Research Model

RESEARCH METHODS

Data Measurement

This research uses 3 variables and can be measured using existing indicators. The measurement indicators in Table 1 are measured on a scale of 1-5 with the understanding that scale 1 strongly disagrees and number 5 indicates the respondent strongly agrees.

Table 1: Measurement

Variable	Indicator	Item Number
	One of our focuses is customer satisfaction	CO1
	An important point in business is after-sales service	CO2
Orientation	We understand our customers' needs and desires	CO3
customer	Our daily activity is the creation of value for customers	CO4
	Our commitment is to serve customers	CO5
Social media	Social media (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, TikTok, Youtube) is useful for providing information about our Company's products and business	SM1
	Social media can decide customer desires and expectations	SM2
	Social media improves sales of our products	SM3
	Social media supports promotional activities for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises	SM4
Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises	Market share has increased over the years last 3 years	SP1
Performance	Sales have always grown for 3 last year	SP2
	Achieved profit growth (profitability) over the last 3 years	SP3

Description:

n = Number of Samples N = Total Population

e = Percentage of inaccuracy allowance due to sampling errors that can still be tolerated, $e = 5\%$ or 0.05

In this study, the population obtained was as large as possible and an error tolerance limit of 5% or e of 0.05 was determined, so the number of research samples could be determined as follows:

$$n = \frac{2.618}{1 + 2.618 (0, 05)^{2 \times}}$$

$$n = \frac{2.618}{7.545}$$

$n = 346.98$ (rounded to 350 respondents), then The sample for this research was 350 respondents.

Data Collection Methods and Sources

The sampling technique used in this research is probability sampling technique with simple random sampling technique. This technique is a method of sampling that is chosen randomly, where every element in the population has the same chance of being selected as a sample. The selected sample will become the sample frame for this research. Data collection carried out in this research used a questionnaire instrument.

The questionnaire was distributed to Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises assisted by Dekopin South Sulawesi in the culinary sector via e-mail for 1 month in April 2023.

Data Analysis Method

Data analysis used in the research was Partial Least Square (PLS).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Profile

Table 2: Is A Profile Description Of The 350 Respondents In This Study.

Statement	Category	f	Percentage(%)
Gender	Male	120	34,3
	Female	230	65,7
Age	<20 years	1	0,3
	21-30 years	34	9,7
	31-40 years	187	53,4
	41-50 years	111	31,7
	>50 years	17	4,9
Educational	Primary school	0	0
	Junior High School	6	1,7
	Senior High School	132	37,7
	Bachelor degree (S1)	157	44,9
Business Category	Bachelor degree (S2/S3)	4	1,1
	Heavy Food	58	17
	Snack Food	217	62
Long Business Establishment	Food and Beverages	31	9
	Drinks	44	12
	>1 years	9	2,6
Total Employees	1-5 years	279	79,7
	6-10 years	53	15,1
	>10 years	9	2,6
Business Income	<10 persons	307	87,7
	11-30 persons	40	11,4
	>30 persons	3	0,9
Business Income	<100 million per year	262	74,9
	100-300 million per year	76	21,7
	1-3 billion per year	0	0
	>3 billion per year	1	0,3

Evaluation of Outer Model Convergent Validity

Tabel 3: Loading Factor

Variable	Indicator	Loading Score	Description
Customer Orientation	CO1	0,912	<i>Valid</i>
	CO2	0,863	<i>Valid</i>
	CO3	0,901	<i>Valid</i>
	CO4	0,834	<i>Valid</i>
	CO5	0,909	<i>Valid</i>
Social media	SM1	0,824	<i>Valid</i>
	SM2	0,757	<i>Valid</i>
	SM3	0,764	<i>Valid</i>
	SM4	0,828	<i>Valid</i>
Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises	SP1	0,904	<i>Valid</i>
	SP2	0,930	<i>Valid</i>
	SP3	0,940	<i>Valid</i>

Based on the results of the loading factor test in Table 3, it shows that all indicators have a loading factor value greater than 0.7, which means that all indicators in this study are valid.

Discriminant Validity

Tabel 4: Cross Loading

	Orientation Customer	Orientation Customer	Orientation Customer
CO1	0,912	0,348	0,474
CO2	0,863	0,340	0,448
CO3	0,901	0,327	0,470
CO4	0,834	0,265	0,366
CO5	0,909	0,352	0,512
SM1	0,278	0,824	0,249
SM2	0,284	0,757	0,189
SM3	0,309	0,764	0,410
SM4	0,296	0,828	0,323
SP1	0,465	0,399	0,904
SP2	0,468	0,318	0,930
SP3	0,502	0,385	0,940

Based on Table 4, it can be shown that the cross loading value of each indicator in this study meets the discriminant validity criteria. This is because the cross loading value is greater than the loading value for other constructs.

Tabel 5: Reliability Test

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Custome Orientation	0,930	0,947	0,782
Social media	0,813	0,872	0,630
Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises	0,915	0,947	0,855

Based on Table 5, it is shown that the Cronbach's alpha value and composite reliability value are >0.7 , and the AVE value is >0.5 , so the variables in this study can be said to be reliable.

Evaluasi Inner Model

Tabel 6: R-Square

Variabel	R Square
Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises	0,318

Based on Table 6, the R-Square value for the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises performance variable is 0.318. So it can be concluded that the R-Square value of the endogenous variable in this study is in the weak category.

Tabel 7: Q-Square

Variabel	Q Square
Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises	0,267

Based on Table 7, the Q-Square predictive relevance value for the performance variable for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises is 0.267. So it can be concluded that the Q-Square predictive relevance value of the endogenous variables in this study is relevant and accurate.

Tabel 8: Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values	Description
$CO \rightarrow SP$	0,437	9,732	$<0,001$	Hypothesis Accepted
$SM \rightarrow SP$	0,253	5,664	$<0,001$	Hypothesis Accepted
$CO \rightarrow SM -SP$	0,023	0,798	0,425	Hypothesis Rejected

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Influence of Customer Orientation (joint business) on the Performance of Small and Medium Micro Enterprises

From the research results shown in Table 8, it can be seen that the influence of customer orientation on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the culinary sector in South Sulawesi during the post-pandemic period is significant with a t-statistic value of 9.241, where this value is greater than the t value -table of 1.96. Apart from that, the path coefficient value is 0.437, which illustrates that the direction of the relationship between the customer orientation variable and the performance variable for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises is positive.

This shows that the stronger the customer orientation of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, the greater the influence on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. These findings are in line with research conducted by Nurfarida et al., (2021) with the result that customer orientation has a positive effect on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. This research is also in line with research conducted by Domi et al. (2020) which shows that customer orientation encourages Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises to use a special approach to respond to and facilitate the needs of their customers, so that ultimately it has an impact on increasing sales and profits of Micro, Small

and Medium Enterprises. On the other hand, this research is not in line with research findings conducted by Brockman et al., (2012) where customer orientation has no effect on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises if the level of risk taking, innovation and opportunity is the low one.

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises that have a low level of risk taking tend not to benefit from customer orientation because they are afraid of the risks involved. Apart from that, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises that have a low level of innovation also tend not to benefit from customer orientation because they are unable to have new concepts and approaches. Such companies tend to be market-driven rather than market-driven. Lastly, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises that have a low level of opportunity tend not to benefit from being customer oriented because they cannot know what customers need, especially those entering new industries.

The Influence of Social Media on the Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

From the research results shown in Table 8, it can be seen that the influence of social media on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the culinary sector in South Sulawesi during the post-pandemic period is significant with a t-statistic value of 5.489, where this value is greater than the t value -table of 1.96. Apart from that, the path coefficient value is 0.253, which illustrates that the direction of the relationship between social media variables and the performance variables of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises is positive.

This shows that the better the use of social media by Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, the greater the influence on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. These findings are in line with research conducted by Nurfarida et al., (2021) with the result that social media adoption has a positive influence on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. The use of e-commerce for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises can also be utilized to develop and achieve organizational goals for both the long and short term so that they can achieve competitive advantage (Nasution et al., 2021). The use of e-commerce is an application of the dynamic capability perspective theory in which to measure, predict and understand an organization's ability to create customer value through innovative use of IT (Wu & Hisa, 2008). The use of e-commerce for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises makes it possible to expand the sales network of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (Nasution et al., 2021) including promotional activities and advertising of services or products sold and electronic delivery (Al-Bakri & Katsiolouides , 2015).

This research is also in line with research conducted by Fan et al. (2021) where Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises that invest in social media get more benefits. The use of social media by Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises will provide a competitive advantage for their users. However, the findings in this research are not in line with research conducted by Ahmad et al. (2019), where research conducted shows that social media adoption has no effect on company performance. The use of social media as an experimental tool cannot be quickly measured for success. Therefore, the use of social media will provide added value if its use is to support existing business strategies, rather than making social media adoption the main strategy.

The Influence of Joint Business/Customer Orientation on the Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises with Social Media as a Moderating Variable

From the research results shown in Table 8, it can be seen that the influence of customer orientation on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the culinary sector in South Sulawesi during the pandemic with the social media variable as a moderating variable is not significant with a t-statistic value of 0.732. where this value is smaller than the t-table value of 1.96.

Apart from that, the path coefficient value is 0.023, which illustrates that the direction of the relationship between the customer orientation variable and the performance variable for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises with the social media variable as a moderating variable is positive.

This shows that the social media variable as a moderator does not strengthen the relationship between joint business/customer orientation and the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. These findings are not in line with research conducted by Nurfarida et al., (2021) with the result that customer orientation has a positive effect on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises with social media as a moderating variable.

The findings from this research support the statement according to Trainor (2012) where it is stated that resources such as software or hardware, in this case owned social media, will not have a significant impact on improving the performance of a company if their use is not optimal. Companies that invest in software or hardware will not feel a significant impact on their business if the human resources' ability to operate it is not trained and developed.

Apart from that, the training carried out by Dekopin South Sulawesi, namely Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Champion in 2023, was not carried out optimally. This was because the Covid-19 pandemic was severe at that time. This situation meant that the training provided by Dekopin South Sulawesi to its mentors, including Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the culinary sector, only lasted one month, compared to what was originally scheduled for six months.

The interaction between the joint business/customer orientation variable and social media does not have a significant influence on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. This shows that the social media variable with technology transfer aspects of digital marketing is a moderating predictor variable. This means that social media through digital marketing as a moderating variable in this case only plays a role as a predictor variable or by another name, namely a free independent variable in the relationship model being developed.

CONCLUSION

- 1) The research results show that customer orientation (joint business) and social media (digital marketing) have a significant effect on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. However, on the other hand, this research shows the results that social media cannot moderate the relationship between customer orientation and the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. That by being customer oriented and adopting social media for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises players can improve company performance, where these findings support previous research. However, there is one finding that does not support previous research, because the results are that social media cannot moderate the relationship between customer orientation and the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. This is a very interesting finding because there are not many theories and research that discuss social media as a moderating variable between customer orientation and the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises.
- 2) Customer orientation and social media adoption are strategies to survive in uncertain situations. However, the role of social media must be strengthened and discussed again because in this research it has not been proven that it can support the activities of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises to carry out customer-oriented strategies.
- 3) Joint business/customers influence the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises are expected to continue to consistently pay attention to their customers as input. These inputs can be used as business strategies for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the post-Covid-19 pandemic period so that they can survive in uncertain situations. Apart from that, this research also shows that social media has an influence on business performance. Micro, Small and Medium. However, on the other hand, social media cannot moderate the relationship between customer orientation and the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises are also expected to use social media not only for company branding, but for more than that, such as interacting with their customers, so that two-way communication can occur between Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises and consumers.

References

- 1) Abdullah, D., Harristhana, A., Sastraatmadja, M., & Lestari, N. C. (2023). *Cendikia : Media Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Implementation of youtube asa learning media in the new normal era*. 13(3),476–481.
- 2) Ahmad, S. Z., Abu Bakar, A. R., & Ahmad, N. (2019). Social media adoption and its impact on firm performance: the case of the UAE. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 25(1), 84–111. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEBR-08-2017-0299>
- 3) Akmeshe, H., Aras, S., & Akmeshe, K. (2016). Financial Performance and Social Media: A Research on Tourism Enterprises Quoted in Istanbul Stock Exchange (BIST). *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 39(November 2015), 705–710. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671\(16\)30281-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671(16)30281-7)

- 4) Al-Bakri, A. A., & Katsioloudes, M. I. (2015). The factors affecting e-commerce adoption by Jordanian SMEs. *Management Research Review*, 38(7), 726–749. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-12-2013-0291>
- 5) Anber, H., Salah, A., & El-aziz, A. A. A. (2016). A literature review on Twitter data analysis. *International Journal of Computer and Electrical Engineering*, 8(3), 241–249.
- 6) Atmoko, B. D. (2012). *Instagram Handbook*. Jakarta: Mediakita.
- 7) Bella, A. (2018). *100 Tahun Ekonomi Indonesia Ada di Tangan Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah Jabar*. Retrieved from Marketeers. [https://www.marketeers.com/100-tahun-ekonomi-indonesia-ada-di-tangan-Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah-jabar](https://www.marketeers.com/100-tahun-ekonomi-indonesia-ada-di-tangan-Usaha-Mikro-Kecil-Dan-Menengah-jabar)
- 8) Brockman, B. K., Jones, M. A., & Becherer, R. C. (2012). Customer orientation and performance in small firms: Examining the moderating influence of risk-taking, innovativeness, and opportunity focus. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 50(3), 429–446. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-627X.202.00361x>
- 9) Choudhary, N., Gautam, C., Arya, V., Kangri, G., & Haridwar, V. (2020). *Reference to Tiktok-A New Rising Social Media. October*.
- 10) CNNIndonesia. (2021). *16,4 Juta Pelaku Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah Sudah Terhubung ke Platform Digital*. CNNIndonesia. Retrieved from [https://www.cnnindonesia.com/ekonomi/20211209105019-92-731873/164-juta-pelaku-Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah- sudah-terhubung-ke-platform-digital](https://www.cnnindonesia.com/ekonomi/20211209105019-92-731873/164-juta-pelaku-Usaha-Mikro-Kecil-Dan-Menengah-sudah-terhubung-ke-platform-digital)
- 11) Dharmawati, M. (2016). *Kewirausahaan*. Depok: Rajawali Pers.
- 12) Domi, S., Capelleras, J. L., & Musabelliu, B. (2020). Customer orientation and SME performance in Albania: A case study of the mediating role of innovativeness and innovation behavior. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 26(1), 130–146. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356766719867374>
- 13) Eisenhardt, K. M., & Martin, J. A. (2000). Dynamic capabilities: What are they? *Strategic Management Journal*.
- 14) Fan, M., Qalati, S. A., Aamir, M., Khan, S., Mir, S.,
- 15) Shah, M., Ramzan, M., & Khan, R. S. (2021). Effects of entrepreneurial orientation on social media adoption and SME performance: The moderating role of innovation capabilities. *Plos One*, 16(4), e0247320. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0247320>
- 16) Islam, M. Z., & Zhe, Z. (2022). The effect of customer orientation on financial performance in service firms: The mediating role of service innovation. *Management Science Letters*, 12(2), 101–116. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2021.10.003>
- 17) Lin, Y., & Wu, L. Y. (2014). Exploring the role of dynamic capabilities in firm performance under the resource-based view framework. *Journal of Business Research*,
- 18) Lubis, P. A., Azmi, Z., & Suriyanti, L. H. (2020). Pengaruh customer accounting dan customer orientation terhadap kinerja organisasi. *Jurnal Al- Iqtishad*.
- 19) Maulidah, W. (2021). *Digitalisasi Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah untuk Pemulihan Ekonomi Daerah*. Retrieved from Media Indonesia. [https://mediaindonesia.com/opini/435590/digitalisasi-Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah-untuk- pemulihan-ekonomi-daerah](https://mediaindonesia.com/opini/435590/digitalisasi-Usaha-Mikro-Kecil-Dan-Menengah-untuk-pemulihan-ekonomi-daerah)
- 20) Nasrullah, R. (2015). *Media Sosial : Perspektif Komunikasi, Budaya, dan Sosioteknologi*. Bandung: Simbiosis Rekatama Media.
- 21) Nasution, M. D. T. P., Rafiki, A., Lubis, A., & Rossanty, Y. (2021). Entrepreneurial orientation, knowledge management, dynamic capabilities towards e-commerce adoption of SMEs in Indonesia. *Journal of Science and Technology Policy Management*.
- 22) Neneh, B. N. (2018). Customer orientation and SME performance: the role of networking ties. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 9(2), 178–196.

- 23) Nurfarida, I. N., Sarwoko, E., & Arief, M. (2021). The Impact of social media adoption on customer orientation and SME performance: An empirical study in Indonesia. *Journal of Asian Finance*, 8(6), 357–0365.
- 24) Nurranirusmana. (2022). *Dinas KUK Jabar Targetkan Cetak 4.000 Pelaku Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah Juara*. Retrieved from Jabarekspres.Com.
- 25) Pusparisa, Y. (2020). *Beralih ke Pemasaran Digital, Siasat Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah Bangkit dari Krisis*. Retrieved from Databoks.
- 26) Situmorang, J. R. (2018). Mengenal lebih dalam apa itu kapabilitas dinamik. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 14(1), 20–27. <https://journal.unpar.ac.id/index.php/JurnalAdministrasiBisnis/article/view/3846>
- 27) Trainor, K. J. (2012). Relating social media technologies to performance: A capabilities-based perspective. *Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management*,
- 28) Wijayanto, N. (2021). *Ridwan Kamil: Digitalisasi Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah Tumbuh 40% di Jawa Barat*. Retrieved from SINDONEWS.
- 29) Wu, J. H., & Hisa, T. L. (2008). Developing e-business dynamic capabilities: An analysis of e-commerce innovation from I-, M-, to U-commerce. *Journal of Organizational Computing and Electronic Commerce*.
- 30) Zhu, Z., & Nakata, C. (2007). Reexamining the link between customer orientation and business performance: The role of information systems. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*.
- 31) Ziggers, G. W., & Henseler, J. (2016). The reinforcing effect of a firm's customer orientation and supply-base orientation on performance. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 52, 18–26.